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Data-Driven Chemical-Physical Soil Quality Index And Visualization Tool

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Abstract. Soil quality assessment is fundamental for sustainable agricultural management but is complicated by the variability, complexity, and long-term dynamics of soil properties. This study developed a soil quality index using a data-driven class-modelling approach based on the Data-Driven Soft Independent Model of Class Analogy (DD-SIMCA).

A reference model was created from a synthetic dataset representing typical ranges of nine physico-chemical parameters of agricultural soils. The model was then applied to a real dataset of approximately 9,800 soil samples. Classification performance was excellent (sensitivity = 1), enabling clear categorization into distinct soil quality classes.

To enhance usability, results were converted into a colour-coded QR code, providing an intuitive visual summary of soil quality for practitioners. Further validation will use harmonized datasets from the Varda Foundation's SoilHive platform, supporting scalability across regions and pedo-climatic contexts.

Integration within SoilHive will ensure continuous model refinement as new data are contributed. Overall, the framework demonstrates the potential of machine-learning-based class modelling to support robust, scalable, and user-friendly soil quality assessment in agricultural systems.

Keywords: soil quality evaluation, DD-SIMCA, digital agriculture, decision support system, agricultural management.